

INFLUENCE OF TRANSIENT RADIATIVE HEAT FLUX ON DEGREE OF CRYSTALLINITY IN THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

Mark Smeets^a, Arian Tashakori^a, Sandesh Amgai^a, Vishnu V Ganesan^a, Ankur Jain^a, Paul Davidson^a

^a*Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, University of Texas at Arlington, Arlington, TX 7601-0018*

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ABSTRACT

Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) enables high-speed, precise deposition of fiber-reinforced composites, making it ideal for complex, high-performance structures. Understanding the transient thermal behavior of thermoplastic composites during AFP is critical, as it affects bonding, residual stress, and final properties. This study presents a systematic experimental characterization of thermal evolution and resulting crystallinity in CF/LM-PAEK composites exposed to a moving Xenon-arc flash lamp. A robotic setup was developed to map the lamp's irradiance profile, and infrared thermography was used to capture surface temperature during heating. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) measured crystallinity across varying process conditions. Results show that temperature and crystallization are governed by radiant exposure, thermal diffusivity, cooling rates, and process parameters such as power and speed. These insights support improved AFP thermal control and process optimization.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites are widely used in aerospace applications due to their high strength-to-weight ratio. Traditional methods like hand layup are labor-intensive and inefficient [1], whereas Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) enables scalable manufacturing by robotically depositing pre-impregnated CFRP tows with improved precision [2, 3]. Both thermoset and thermoplastic CFRPs can be manufactured via AFP. Thermosets require curing post-laydown, while thermoplastics offer the advantage of in-situ consolidation, eliminating autoclave requirements and shortening cycle times [4–6]. However, controlling crystallinity and achieving strong interlaminar bonding in thermoplastics is challenging due to rapid thermal cycles.

In AFP of thermoplastics, tows must be rapidly heated to 320°C–350°C [7] to allow polymer chain mobility and subsequent crystallization, forming lamellae and spherulites that determine mechanical performance [8, 9]. Studies indicate that rapid cooling reduces crystallinity, while prolonged heating enhances it [10]. Thus, uniform and efficient heating becomes essential. Various non-contact heating systems have been examined, including Hot Gas Torch (HGT) [11–13], induction heating [14–16], and Near-Infrared (NIR) lasers [17–19]. A newer alternative is Xenon-arc flash lamp heating [20–22], which delivers high-energy broadband UV–IR pulses.

Heating strategies strongly affect temperature gradients and resulting microstructure. Tafreshi et al. [12] showed that while HGT effectively heats the surface, inner plies remain under-heated. Similarly, Shafaq et al. [23] linked cooling rate variations to crystallinity fluctuations. Laser heating improves interlaminar bonding but has limited penetration, causing lower crystallinity in core plies [24]. Xenon-arc flash lamps, emitting diffuse radiation unlike lasers' collimated beams, may enable better thermal penetration and uniformity [25]. However, few studies to date explore their behavior and process optimization in AFP.

Challenges in Xenon-arc flash AFP heating include energy distribution control, consistent material exposure, and understanding crystallization effects. Heating effectiveness is governed by the radiative heat flux and the temperature evolution rate in the laydown zone [7]. While prior studies have used thermocouples [26], fiber Bragg gratings [27], and IR thermography [28, 29] to map AFP thermal profiles, limited data exists on Xenon-arc systems. Danezis et al. [30] developed a 3D optical ray-tracing model to simulate lamp behavior, highlighting the complexity of diffuse source modeling.

This study focuses on the thermal characteristics of Xenon-arc flash heating in AFP. It aims to isolate key parameters—irradiance, exposure time, and thermal response—and quantify their effects on surface temperature and crystallization. A spatially resolved irradiance field is characterized and linked to temperature evolution and crystallinity, as measured by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). Experiments are conducted using a KUKA robotic AFP platform, a Xenon-arc flash lamp as the heating source, and LM-PAEK carbon fiber tows as the material system [31]. The results aim to bridge critical gaps in understanding AFP thermal behavior and to optimize Xenon-arc based heating strategies for next-generation thermoplastic composites.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Flux Measurement

A measurement setup was developed to characterize irradiance (E_e) near the Xenon-arc flash lamp of a humm3 heating system [20]. The lamp, enclosed in a 26 mm × 70 mm cavity, was mounted vertically, and irradiance was measured using a water-cooled Gordon gauge heat flux sensor (Hukseflux) mounted on a six-axis robotic arm. The sensor, with a 4.3 mm port and up to 1 MW/m² measurement capacity, recorded data at 200 Hz using a DI-245 system (Dataq). Irradiance output was controlled by adjusting pulse width (t_p), while keeping voltage (200 V) and frequency (90 Hz) constant. Based on the relation $P = I_e \omega t_p V$, with $I_e = 230$ A, pulse widths of 0.3 ms, 1 ms, and 1.7 ms yielded power outputs of 1240 W, 4132 W, and 7025 W, respectively.

A KUKA robotic arm, programmed using Grasshopper UI in Rhino 7, was used to move a heat flux sensor through a 3D grid above the Xenon-arc flash lamp. At each grid point, the sensor held position for four seconds to record voltage, which was averaged and converted to irradiance. Measurements were taken from 36 mm to 12 mm vertically (Z-axis), and across a 52 mm × 36 mm area in the horizontal plane (X-Y), with 4 mm step sizes. Due to housing constraints, data below 12 mm was linearly extrapolated.

Three power levels (1240 W, 4132 W, and 7025 W) were tested. A full 3D irradiance field was mapped at 4132 W using 1078 measured and 462 extrapolated points, covering one quadrant and mirrored to form the full field. Radial Basis interpolation in Python was used to generate the 3D irradiance map, which was then scaled linearly for the other two power levels. This enabled development of a power-based scaling law for estimating irradiance fields between 1240 W and 7025 W.

2.2 Thermal Measurement

Following irradiance field characterization, a new setup was implemented to measure the surface temperature profile on a CF/LM-PAEK panel (VICTREX AE™ 250 UDT) as the Xenon-arc flash lamp moved across it. A FLIR A655sc infrared camera operating in the 7.5–14 μm spectral range at 60 Hz captured real-time thermal data during lamp traversal at various speeds (Figure 1).

The setup included a four-rod frame supporting a panel made of ten evenly spaced CF/LM-PAEK tows, secured using double-sided tape. The lamp, mounted on the robot arm, moved along a path aligned with the center of the panel and tows, ensuring radiation incidence was normal to the surface. The fiber direction matched the direction of lamp motion. The IR camera was positioned to monitor the full temperature field, while a flux sensor placed beneath the panel verified irradiance during lamp motion. The robot's path was carefully calibrated to ensure accurate tracking over the panel.

The interpolated irradiance field guided the selection of a 28 mm lamp height for the moving lamp experiments—sufficient to avoid blocking the thermal camera's view. The robotic arm was programmed to traverse a path beyond the lamp's irradiance footprint, ensuring full coverage over the CF/LM-PAEK tows (Figure 1).

Twelve tests were conducted in two phases. The first phase studied how varying speeds affected surface temperature evolution. For lamp powers of 2066 W, 4132 W, and 7025 W, speeds of 200, 300, and 400 mm/s were tested (nine experiments). The second phase aimed to reach the optimal crystallization temperature range (320–340 °C). Speeds were adjusted accordingly: 35 mm/s (2066 W), 130 mm/s (4132 W), and 210 mm/s (7025 W), with additional runs at 100 mm/s and 500 mm/s (4132 W).

Each test followed a consistent procedure: the lamp was set to simmer mode, IR recording began, then after five seconds, the lamp switched to flash mode and the robot initiated motion. The FLIR camera recorded the full heating and cooling cycle, while the flux sensor captured irradiance over time to validate the empirical irradiance model. A new panel was used for each test and preserved for post-experiment material characterization.

2.3 Material Characterization

After the moving lamp experiments, the irradiated CF/LM-PAEK tows within a panel were sectioned to measure the degree of crystallization corresponding to their distance from the lamp, the lamp power, and the lamp speed across the tow. The tows which exceeded the glass transition (T_g) temperature of 150 °C were considered for Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and further analysis. Certain experiments were excluded from material analysis, since the panel never exceeded the T_g . These experiments were: 200 mm/s, 300 mm/s, and 400 mm/s for a power of 2066 W and 500 mm/s for a power of 4132 W.

For each measurement, a hole puncher was used to cut out a disc in the center of an irradiated tow. For the DSC measurements, temperature sweep was set from 40 °C to 360 °C at a rate of 10 °C/m. For all experiments, only tows 1-3 were chosen, since these crossed the T_g threshold. A total of 33 samples were analyzed using DSC including the three as-received pristine (unheated) samples and three oven-baked samples. The pristine samples represented the lower benchmark of CF/LM-PAEK tape crystallinity. On the other hand, the oven-baked samples represented the upper benchmark of crystallinity through a slow heating and cooling process, allowing for increased spherulite growth [33]. Specifically, the oven-baked samples were heated to 310 °C and held at 280 °C for 60 minutes. The samples were then cooled at a rate of 18 °C/min to room temperature. Crystallinity in each sample was estimated using the following standard procedure [10]:

Bulk crystallization is a result of multiple factors during the experiments, but is most influenced by the resulting temperature-time profile during the cooling phase. The temperature data from the IR camera for each experiment was converted to a multidimensional array. Each pixel at any location on the tows exhibited a heating and cooling phase, and is easily extracted for analysis.

3 SUMMARY OF RESULTS

3.1 Irradiance Field Characterization

A 3D irradiance field around the Xenon-arc flash lamp (at 4132 W) was generated using Radial Basis Function interpolation (Figure 2). The irradiance profile revealed a conical decay from the lamp center, dropping from ~ 0.7 MW/m² near the origin to ~ 0.2 MW/m² at 20 mm. While the spatial shape remained consistent across power levels, magnitudes scaled with a third-order polynomial function accounting for voltage, frequency, and pulse width. This enables prediction of transient irradiance at any speed or location on the panel.

3.2 Transient Irradiance and Radiant Exposure

As the lamp traverses the panel, the irradiance on a point varies over time. Radiant exposure (H_e) is computed by integrating irradiance over exposure time. Experimental validation with a flux sensor confirmed strong correlation with the predicted irradiance. Increasing lamp speed narrows the irradiance profile and reduces peak irradiance. Multiple combinations of power and speed can yield the same radiant exposure (Figure 3).

3.3 Temperature Evolution Across the Panel

IR camera measurements show that the surface temperature lags behind the peak irradiance due to thermal diffusion (Figure 4). At high speeds and powers (e.g., 7025 W at 400 mm/s), the temperature front moves slower than the lamp, with increasing lag. Table 1 summarizes this lag, showing temperature front speeds are typically 30–67% of the lamp speed, decreasing with higher lamp power.

3.4 Linking Temperature, Radiant Exposure, and Speed

Bubble plots (Figure 5) reveal that even with equal radiant exposure, different power-speed combinations yield different peak temperatures due to location effects and thermal inertia. Tow 1 (closest to the lamp center) did not always show the highest temperature, likely due to dynamic heat accumulation and loss mechanisms. There is no one-to-one mapping between radiant exposure and peak temperature—thermal response is a function of power, speed, and thermal transport properties.

3.5 Crystallinity Trends

DSC analysis showed only slight increases in crystallinity across samples compared to the as-received material. The highest crystallinity (5.45%) was obtained at 7025 W and 200 mm/s. Most experimental runs yielded crystallinity in the 2.4–3.3% range, similar or slightly above baseline. Oven-baked samples reached much higher crystallinity (18.8%) due to longer controlled cooling. Key factors influencing crystallinity were maximum temperature and cooling duration. However, given the short exposure and rapid cooling inherent to AFP, significant increases in crystallinity are limited without further thermal management (Figure 6).

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study developed a systematic method to quantify the thermal history and resulting crystallinity of CF/LM-PAEK composite tape heated by a Xenon-arc flash lamp. A robotic test setup was used to map the 3D irradiance field and then simulate a moving heat source over a stationary panel. The resulting transient temperature behavior was captured using infrared thermography, and the crystallinity outcomes were analyzed via DSC.

Key findings include:

- A complete irradiance field model was created using robotic measurements, RBF interpolation, and a power-based scaling law, enabling prediction under any lamp setting.
- A clear thermal lag was observed between lamp motion and temperature front, which increases with speed.
- Radiant exposure depends on lamp power, position, and speed; different parameter combinations can result in the same exposure.
- Peak material temperature correlates with radiant exposure and spatial position, not just power and speed, making simple process control insufficient.
- DSC results showed that rapid cooling under the Xenon-arc leads to crystallinity levels significantly lower than those achieved via slow cooling, even when peak temperatures exceeded the melt point.

Overall, the study underscores the need for precise thermal control in AFP of thermoplastics. The experimental framework established here lays the foundation for predictive modeling of thermal behavior and microstructure evolution in advanced manufacturing of CF/LM-PAEK composites.

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Table 1: Maximum temperature achieved (T_m) for combinations of lamp speed (S_L), speed of maximum temperature front (S_T), and maximum temperature of tape achieved (T_m)

P (W)	S_L (mm/s)	S_T (mm/s)	T_m (°C)
2066	35	33.33	339.3
2066	200	175	107.2
2066	300	271.43	83.5
2066	400	354.17	66.9
4132	100	93.75	406
4132	130	125	315.5
4132	200	189.58	238
4132	300	287.5	178.1
4132	400	341.67	143.26
7025	200	183.93	399.3
7025	290	275.34	321.6
7025	300	277.68	292.9
7025	400	360.71	248.6

Figure 1: Left: Experimental setup for CFRP tows exposed to irradiance. The KUKA robot (1) controls the movement of the Xenon-arc flash lamp (2). The thermal camera (3) records surface temperature of the tows mounted to a fixture (4). On the fixture, a flux sensor and the first tow are aligned with the straight move path of the lamp.

Figure 2: Measured irradiance envelope around the Xenon-arc flash lamp for a power of 4132 W . Dotted white line depicts the lamp head cavity.

Figure 3: Irradiance profile with the same radiant exposure of 141 KJ/m² at tow 1 center for difference power and speeds of [7025 W , 200 mm/s],[4132 W , 100 mm/s],[2066 W , 35 mm/s].

Figure 4: Progression of the surface temperature of CFRP tows subjected to radiation from a moving Xenon- arc flash lamp with a speed of 130 mm/s and power set to 4132 W. Surface temperatures shown are taken at a) $t = 0$ s, b) $t = 0.46$ s and c) $t = 0.92$ s. (d-f) are the corresponding temperatures measured across the length of the first tow directly below the lamp's path. The vertical green lines represents the position of the lamp's center while the vertical orange line represents the peak temperature front moving across the tow for the three frames. Solid red line refers to temperature, and solid blue line refers to irradiance across tow 1 due to lamp motion.

Figure 5: Bubble plot showing variation of temperature with radiant exposure. Bubble size represents the speed of lamp motion.

Figure 6: Measured crystallinity for tows 1-3 of all experiments with respect to a) Maximum Temperature and b) cooling duration from peak temperature to 150C.